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POWDER MICROSCOPICAL EVALUATION - INGREDIENTS OF TRIMADA

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Abstract

In the present era, the demand of the herbal product is increased which consecutively leads in increased demand of raw materials. Now a days, to compensate the demand of raw materials, along with the production, adulteration and substitution is also increased. So, it is important to keep the check on this. So, here pharmacognosy of the drug plays an important role. Powder microscopy is the part of the pharmacognosy and it helps to check the impurities and also helps in authentication of the drug. Powders are widely used for most of the preparations. Powder microscopy provides the means to assess and standardized herbal powder which ultimately leads to authentication of herbal drug. **Material & Method:** Powder microscopy of *Trimada* was carried out. *Trimada* is an ayurvedic formulation containing *Chitraka* (*Plumbago zeylanica* Linn.), *Musta* (*Cyperus rotundus* Linn.) and *Vidanga* (*Embelia ribes* Burm.f.). Slides of each ingredient of *Trimada* were prepared using required reagents and observed under the microscope. **Observation & Result:** Powder microscopy of *Trimada* shows fibers, fragments of tissues, fragments of vessels, trichomes, crystals and starch grains. **Discussion and Conclusion:** The microscopic structures which are observed in *Trimada* helps in the correct identification of *Chitraka* (*Plumbago zeylanica* Linn.), *Musta* (*Cyperus rotundus* Linn.) and *Vidanga* (*Embelia ribes* Burm.f.). Powder microscopy helps to standardized the herbal drug and thus making it suitable for the market use.

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INTRODUCTION

Now a days the use of herbal drugs in global market has been surged up. In every sector i.e., pharmaceutical, cosmeceuticals, nutraceutical, etc herbal drugs are used widely. In present era, due to high demand of the herbal drugs, adulteration and substitution is commonly seen by the pharmaceutical companies and traders. So, to keep a check on this and to achieve good therapeutic efficacy, Pharmacognosy plays an important role. Powder microscopy is a part of pharmacognosy and it is the simplest, easiest and most economical way for the authentication as well as standardization of the herbal drug.

To get the maximum therapeutic efficacy it is important to use the specific herbal drugs mentioned in the texts. If it is manipulated in any way then the desired action is not achieved. So, to detect contaminants and for identification of herbal drug, powder microscopy is essential. Here, for the present study *Trimada* is selected for the powder microscopy. *Trimada* is an important polyherbal formulation of the Ayurved.¹ It contains *Chitraka* (*Plumbago zeylanica* Linn. Family - Plumbaginaceae), *Musta* (*Cyperus rotundus* Linn. Family - Cyperaceae) and *Vidanga* (*Embelia ribes* Burm.f. Family - Myrsinaceae).

AIM:

To analyse the microscopic features in the powder of *Trimada*.

OBJECTIVE:

1. To assess the microscopic features such as fibres, tissues, vascular bundles, starch grains, trichomes etc. in the powder of *Chitraka* (*Plumbago zeylanica* Linn.), *Musta* (*Cyperus rotundus* Linn.) and *Vidanga* (*Embelia ribes* Burm.f.)
2. To compare the assessed features of herbal drugs with their standards mentioned in authentic reference.

MATERIALS & METHODS:

Trimada was used for the powder microscopy. *Trimada* is an ayurvedic formulation containing *Chitraka* (*Plumbago zeylanica* Linn.), *Musta* (*Cyperus rotundus* Linn.) and *Vidanga* (*Embelia ribes* Burm.f.). Roots of *Chitraka* (*Plumbago zeylanica* Linn.), rhizome of *Musta* (*Cyperus rotundus* Linn.) and fruits of *Vidanga* (*Embelia ribes* Burm.f.) were collected and powdered following the standard operating procedure.

Slide preparation:

Slides of each ingredient of *Trimada* were prepared separately using required reagents and observed under the microscope to assess their various microscopic features. Microscopic characters observed were compared with the standards mentioned in authentic reference.²⁻⁴

Staining agents: Safranin and iodine

OBSERVATIONS & DISCUSSION:

Table No.: Powder microscopic characters found in *Trimada*

No.	Microscopic characters	<i>Chitraka</i>	<i>Musta</i>	<i>Vidanga</i>
1.	Fragments of fibres	+	-	-
2.	Tissue cell	+	+	+
3.	Vessel element	+	+	-

4.	Fragments of tangentially cut medullary rays	+	-	-
5.	Starch Grains	+	-	-
6.	Trichome	+	-	-

Table No.: Powder microscopic study of *Chitraka (Plumbago zeylanica Linn.)*

No.	Characteristics of <i>Chitraka</i>	Figure no.
1.	Fragments of fibres	1,2
2.	Fragments of vessels	3
3.	Fragments of tangentially cut medullary rays	4
4.	Fragments of parenchyma	5
5.	Starch Grains	6

Table No.: Powder microscopic study of *Musta (Cyperus rotundus Linn)*

No.	Characteristics of <i>Musta</i>	Figure no.
1.	Vessel element with spiral thickening	1,2
2.	Tissue fragments with thin-walled cells	3
3.	Starch Grains	4

Table No.: Powder microscopic study of *Vidanga (Embelia ribes Burm.f.)*

No.	Characteristics of <i>Vidanga</i>	Figure no.
1.	Dark brown coloured palisade like cells of the endocarp	1
2.	Sclerieds of mesocarp	2
3.	Stone cells of mesocarp	3
4.	Cells of the endosperm filled with aleurone grains of fixed oil	4
5.	Dark brown coloured cells of the perisperm	5

Through this present study information regarding the microscopic characters of the herbal drug can be known. For this microscopic study, powder of *Trimada* was selected. The microscopic characters of *Trimada* were observed which will be narrated further. Powder microscopy of *Chitraka (Plumbago zeylanica Linn.)* shows, fragments of fibers, fragments of parenchyma, fragments of vessels, fragments of tangentially cut medullary rays, starch grains and trichome. Powder microscopy of *Musta (Cyperus rotundus Linn)* shows vessel element with vessel element with spiral thickening, tissue fragments with thin-walled cells and starch grains. Powder microscopy of *Vidanga (Embelia ribes Burm.f.)* shows, dark

brown coloured palisade like cells of the endocarp, Sclerieds of mesocarp, stone cells, cells of the endosperm filled with aleurone grains of fixed oil and dark brown-coloured cells of the perisperm.

Standardization of compound formulations of Ayurved is quite difficult and complicated. But it is essential for assuring the quality and safety of herbal drugs thus making herbal drugs viable for the use. In this present study, powder microscopy of each ingredient of *Trimada* was carried out and their microscopic characters were noted. These characters might help in detecting impurities and exact identification of material available from the market.

Powder microscopic study of *Chitraka (Plumbago zeylanica Linn.)*

Fig 5

Fragment of parenchyma

Starch Grain

Fig 6

Powder microscopic study of *Musta* (*Cyperus rotundus* Linn)

Fig 1

Fig 2

Fig 3

Fig 4

Starch Grain

Powder microscopic study of *Vidanga (Embelia ribes Burm.f.)*

Fig 1: Dark brown colour palisade like cells of the endocarp

Fig 2: Sclerieds of mesocarp

Fig 3: Stone cells of mesocarp

Fig 4: Cells of the endosperm

Fig 5: Cells of the perisperm

CONCLUSION:

The current study's finding aid in the identification of *Trimada*. According to the observations, microscopic characters such as fragments of fibers, fragments of vessels, fragments of tangentially cut medullary rays, fragments of parenchyma and starch grains indicates the presence of *Chitraka (Plumbago zeylanica Linn.)*. Microscopic characters such as vessel element with spiral thickening, tissue fragments with thin-walled cells and starch grains indicates the presence of *Musta (Cyperus rotundus Linn.)*. Microscopic characters such as dark brown coloured palisade like cells of the endocarp, sclerieds of mesocarp, stone cells of mesocarp, cells of the endosperm filled with aleurone grains of fixed oil and dark brown-coloured cells of the perisperm indicates the presence of *Vidanga (Embelia ribes Burm.f.)*. Any other microscopic character if present or missing other than which are observed then there maybe the chance of adulteration in the compound. Thus, powder microscopy of herbal drug should be carried out before it is introduced in the pharmaceutical market and hospitals for strengthening the health of population.

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